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Consumers' willingness-to-buy pasta with microalgae proteins – Which label can promote sales?

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ABSTRACT

As the world population grows, the demand for protein-rich foods increases. Food manufacturers are looking for new sources of protein, such as microalgae, to meet this increasing demand. Since this type of protein is still relatively unknown among consumers, it is relevant to determine consumers' willingness to pay for foods with microalgae proteins. Moreover, there is more interest in front-of-pack labels nowadays and the potential impact of front-of-pack sustainability labels on willingness to pay for foods containing microalgae proteins is largely unknown. Data were collected through a quantitative online survey ($n = 3027$) including a discrete choice experiment in the Netherlands, Germany, Hungary, Spain, and Italy. Willingness to pay for front-of-pack labels on pasta with microalgae proteins – the focal product concept of this study – was investigated using a discrete choice experiment followed by estimation with a random parameter logit model. Respondents were removed from the total sample because of their opting out reason, leaving a sample of 2880 respondents whose data were used in the DCE-analysis. Respondents who opted out of the DCE for various reasons were not included in the DCE-analysis, leaving a sample of 2880 respondents. Respondents were willing to pay the most for an organic label, followed by the Nutri-Score label, and the vegan label on pasta with microalgae proteins. The resulting policy implications show how labelling with the Nutri-Score, organic label or vegan label can contribute to a more nutritious and sustainable diet.

1. Introduction

As the world's population grows, so does the need for nutritious food, especially protein-rich food (Henchion et al., 2017). In the past, people relied mainly on proteins of animal origin, especially from meat and dairy. However, animal protein production is presented as unsustainable, contributing to greenhouse gas emissions and deforestation (Dagvos & Voordouw, 2013; Devenyns, 2020). Therefore, health institutions and governments are working on the transition to more sustainable protein sources, including plant- or insect-based proteins (Reipurth et al., 2019). Since microalgae have only recently been introduced in the European Union (EU), market uptake of traditional foods, like pasta, with microalgae ingredients is still at an early stage

(Mendes et al., 2022). For market uptake, it is important for producers to know consumers' willingness to pay for their products (Moro et al., 2015), as this helps to estimate the economic profit they can expect when selling these products. This study aims to evaluate the impact of three types of front-of-pack labels on consumers' willingness to pay and the influencing factors related to attitudes, sociodemographic characteristics, and dietary habits. In addition, differences between respondents who chose to purchase versus who opted out four or more times were analysed.

Microalgae proteins were recently introduced to the European food market. The strains *Arthrospira*, better known by its trade name *Spirulina*, and *Chlorella* are the most cultivated microalgae species and currently dominate the food market in dried form (Araújo et al., 2021).

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Microalgae proteins have several advantages over currently used animal and plant proteins. First, the amount of land required to grow microalgae is less than livestock (De Vries & De Boer, 2010; Van Krimpen et al., 2013) and crops such as soybeans and peas (Smetana et al., 2017). Microalgae do not require land for cultivation, have low freshwater consumption, and can grow in saltwater or even wastewater (Li et al., 2019). Regarding the protein quality of microalgae, both *Spirulina* and *Chlorella* have the potential to meet essential amino acid requirements for humans as recommended by the World Health Organization because they contain proteins with a balanced amino acid profile (Becker, 2007; Chronakis & Madsen, 2011). The incorporation of microalgae in foods can increase the nutritional value of these foods. For example, the addition of *Spirulina* to snacks resulted in an increase in nutrient content of 22.6% for proteins, 28.1% for lipids, and 46.4% for minerals (Lucas et al., 2018). It is worth highlighting that pasta has been widely used as a food matrix for microalgae supplementation (De Marco et al., 2014; Fradique et al., 2010) and is commercially available (Villaró et al., 2021). Moreover, corn extrudates with *Spirulina* were appreciated at sensory level based on shape, color, aroma, taste, and crispiness (Tańska et al., 2017) and *Spirulina*-enriched snacks showed 82% sensory acceptance based on aroma, color, taste, and texture (Lucas et al., 2018).

However, foods with microalgae proteins are still relatively unknown to consumers and little attention has been paid to the willingness to pay (WTP) for foods with microalgae- proteins and the impact of ingredient, nutrition, and sustainability labels. This information is critical for the successful introduction of new foods to the market, as pointed out by Bornkessel et al. (2011). WTP for foods is influenced by several factors, including demographic characteristics, health claims, trust in foods, and trust in the technology used to produce them (Plasek & Temesi, 2019). A widely recognised approach to analyse WTP is the use of a Discrete Choice Experiment (DCE), which has been used extensively in food consumption and marketing research, particularly for organic foods (Probst et al., 2012; Zanolini et al., 2013; Lizin et al., 2022) and foods with eco-labels (Jaeger & Rose, 2008). DCE is a method that aims to uncover the attributes that determine food producer or consumer preferences by asking respondents to make sequential choices between alternative products described by changing attributes (Gracia et al., 2009). To date, there are a limited number of studies on WTP for promoting foods with microalgae through nutrition, sustainability, and ingredient labels or programs. For example, studies have reported that consumers prefer meat substitute products with microalgae proteins when these products are organic (Weinrich & Elshiewy, 2019).

Front-of-pack labels (FOP) appear as symbols and provide a simple indication of the nutritional value or environmental impact of the food. These labels can be divided into several categories. Most schemes relate to nutrition, for example, the scheme presented by van Kleef and Dagevos (2015) is based on food health rating. The present study distinguishes between nutritional, environmental, and ingredient labelling. The Nutri-Score label is an upcoming FOP label that is already supported by the EU countries of Belgium, France, Germany, Luxembourg, the Netherlands, Spain, and Switzerland (BEUC, 2021) and is being considered as a potential candidate for the mandatory FOP labelling system in the EU. The Nutri-Score A label was included in this study because this is the most common Nutri-Score label on commercial vegan dry pasta. The Nutri-Score label increases WTP for healthier foods (Gassler et al., 2023) and the presence of the Nutri-Score increased WTP for breakfast cereals among low-income consumers in the study of Nabec et al. (2019). In the same vein, Sampalean et al. (2021) found that consumers were willing to pay €0.22 more for a 250-gram package of cheese than for the same cheese without a nutritional FOP label. However, the WTP was lower compared to the price premium respondents were willing to pay for the other FOP labels tested, notably the NutriInform battery and the Multiple Traffic Light label.

The (EU) organic label is a widely recognized environmental label that indicates a product's compliance with the EU organic regulation. First, labels indicating organic certification have been assigned a higher

WTP than labels indicating more specific environmental sustainability (Bastounis et al., 2021). Second, several studies have shown that consumers are willing to pay a higher price for pasta with the EU organic label compared to non-organic products. Nilsson and Vahtra (2017) found that consumers were willing to pay a price premium of SEK 79 (about €7.05) per kilo of organic pasta compared to conventional pasta. A study by Krystallis and Chrysosoidis (2005) found a higher WTP of about 41% for organic pasta. Differences in findings across studies can be attributed to a number of factors, such as differences in sample demographics, price range, and methodology used. For example, consumers with higher incomes and consumers who are more concerned about the environment are more likely to pay a higher price for organic products (Loureiro et al., 2001). Some studies also suggest that women have a higher WTP for organic products than men (Bellows et al. 2008; Vecchio et al., 2016), although this gender difference has not been consistently confirmed (Bastounis et al., 2021).

The European Vegan Label is a widely recognized symbol used to identify vegan products and services. A recent study conducted by the European Vegetarian Union (2021) examined the WTP for the vegan label. The study found that consumers seeking vegan products are more willing to pay a price premium if a vegan label is present on a product. Marangon et al. (2016) found that a modest share of 8% of respondents were willing to pay a price premium for vegan breadsticks. The percentage willing to pay a premium for pasta with microalgae proteins was not determined. While several studies were found on WTP for vegan foods, they were mainly about meat substitutes in Asian countries. Therefore, this study fills a gap in the literature by investigating WTP for vegan labelled pasta in Europe.

The aim of this study is first to determine the WTP for FOP labels on pasta with microalgae proteins through a consumer survey using a DCE. The nutrition label 'Nutri-Score A', the sustainability label 'Organic' and the ingredient label 'Vegan' are considered. Differences in WTP for the three labels were examined for consumers with different attitudes, socio-demographics and diets. Finally, the study also addresses differences between consumers who had no preference for foods with microalgae proteins and consumers who had a preference for these products. The findings on the WTP for pasta with microalgae proteins at different prices and labels will help manufacturers of foods with microalgae proteins set a realistic price and implement an effective marketing strategy for their new products, with the overall goal of increasing market acceptance of foods with microalgae proteins. The following two research hypotheses are set forth in connection to the study objectives and based on the literature.

H1: The addition of FOP labels such as the Nutri-Score A, Organic, and Vegan label on pasta with microalgae proteins increases the willingness to pay for pasta with microalgae proteins.

H2: Consumer attitudes, socio-demographic characteristics and dietary patterns have a significant impact on the willingness to pay for pasta with microalgae proteins.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Study design and sampling

The present study was conducted within the ProFuture (Proteins of the Future) project, a five-year project funded by EU Horizon 2020 aiming to scale up microalgae production and prepare the market uptake of microalgae proteins as ingredients for innovative and sustainable food and feed products (<https://www.pro-future.eu>). Ethics approval for the study was granted by the Belgian Ethics Committee of Ghent University Hospital (Reference: BC-10402, August 2021). Collected data were coded in a non-identifiable format and processed anonymously.

Cross-sectional data were collected using an online survey in November 2021 envisaging at least 600 respondents in five EU countries: Germany, the Netherlands, Spain, Italy and Hungary (total n = 3027). These countries were selected based on their geographical

distribution and differences in dietary culture and eating habits. Respondents were recruited by means of probabilistic sampling from the online access proprietary panel of a professional marketing research agency in all five countries. Respondents were between 18 and 75 years old and responsible for the purchase of food within their household. In order to obtain representative national samples, screening criteria were used for gender, age and region corresponding with population distributions. The survey could be completed by respondents anywhere, provided that they had a device with internet connection.

2.2. Questionnaire content

First, general health interest (GHI) was measured using eight statements based on Roininen et al. (1999), e.g. "I am very particular about the healthiness of food I eat". Second, to assess attitudes towards new foods and food innovation, the Food Neophobia scale (FNS) and the Food Technology Neophobia scale (FTNS) were used. A short version of the FNS was used with six items (e.g. "I do not trust new foods") (Ritchey et al., 2003). The FTNS was assessed with four items (e.g. "New food technologies decrease the natural quality of food") similar to Verbeke (2015). Third, environmental concern was measured by means of six items measuring the New Environmental Paradigm, e.g. "The earth is like a spaceship with only limited room and resources" (Bostrom et al., 2006; Gooch, 1995). For all the statements regarding GHI, FNS, FTNS and environmental concern, respondents could indicate their level of agreement on a five-point interval scale from "strongly disagree" (=1) to "strongly agree" (=5).

Socio-demographics (i.e., age, gender), economic (i.e., household income) and dietary (i.e., no specific diet, flexitarian, pescetarian, vegetarian and vegan) related data were collected at the end of the survey. In this paper, the term veg*n will be used to indicate both vegetarians and vegans.

2.3. Experimental design and attribute choice

A DCE was used to investigate consumers' WTP for pasta with microalgae proteins. This method was chosen for several reasons: the ability to value various attributes simultaneously and analyse marginal WTP for these attributes (Michaud et al., 2013), compatibility with the random utility theory (McFadden, 1986) and similarity to respondents' real purchase decisions (Adamowicz et al., 1998; Lusk et al., 2003).

The product concept used in this study was vegan dry pasta. Pasta (500 g) was used as an example carrier product for microalgae proteins because pasta with microalgae proteins has been shown previously to be well appreciated at the sensory level, already commonly used as a food matrix for the incorporation of microalgae (De Marco et al., 2014; Fra-dique et al., 2010) and its omnipresence and commercial availability even in versions with microalgae proteins.

Four attributes defined pasta with microalgae proteins. First, the attribute 'Price' consisted of four levels as this number has been used frequently for DCEs (Barreiro-Hurlé et al., 2008; Lockshin et al., 2006) and provides the most efficient number of levels in the WTP estimation, since it ensures a balanced design (Van Loo et al., 2011). The first price (€1.84) was the mean price for 500 g of dry vegan pasta found in the four biggest supermarkets within the study countries. The third price (€8.65) was the mean price of dry vegan pasta with microalgae found on European e-commerce websites selling pasta with microalgae. The second (€5.25) and the fourth (€12.06) prices were chosen such that the intervals between the four prices were equal. The second attribute was 'Sustainability label' and this consisted of four levels: 'Organic label', 'Vegan label', 'Both organic and vegan label' and 'No label'. The third attribute was 'Nutrition label' which contained two levels: 'Nutri-Score A' and 'No label'. The fourth and last attribute was color. This attribute was included to refer to product appearance, one of the sensory properties, which is important for food perception and acceptance (Grunert et al., 2003). Foods may have a greenish color when microalgae are used

and it has already been shown that this may be not appreciated by consumers (Beheshtipour et al., 2013). Two levels were considered: 'light to dark yellow' (to reflect the typical color of pasta) and 'yellow to light green' (to reflect the impact on color from adding microalgae protein). An overview of attributes and levels is given in Table 1.

It was assumed that besides the four attributes mentioned, the options are the same. When respondents chose four or more times out of seven the 'Neither of option A nor B' - option, they were asked to report the main reason for doing so. Six possible reasons were presented: "I do not like pasta in general", "I do not want pasta with proteins from microalgae are added", "I did not want to read all the information", "I did not see any difference between the two options", "The two options were too expensive" and "It was too difficult for me to decide". Additionally, it was possible to mention additional self-given reasons.

A brief introduction to the DCE was provided in the survey (Fig. 1). This introduction included a cheap talk script which is used to reduce hypothetical bias (Lusk, 2003; Murphy et al., 2005). The following question was asked for each choice set, "Options A and B represent two different sets of characteristics of vegan dry pasta (e.g., tagliatelle, penne, spirilli) with microalgae proteins. Do you prefer Option A, Option B or 'Neither option A nor B'?"

The choice sets contained two unlabelled alternatives 'Option A' and 'Option B' and a 'Neither option A nor B' or opt-out option to resemble actual purchases. The opt-out option captures the preferences for other labelling information not shown in the choice set as well as for a no-buy option (Hoeftkens et al., 2012). With two four-level attributes (i.e. price and sustainability label) and two dichotomous attributes (nutrition label and color), the full factorial design gave rise to 64 ($4^2 \times 2^2$) unique combinations. The design was simplified in three steps. First, a fractional design was created in order to reduce the possible combinations with JMP 14. The design consisted of 21 distinct choice sets. Second, choice sets were divided into three surveys of seven choice sets each to limit consumers' cognitive burden (Bech et al., 2011). Third, survey randomisation was used to randomly assign each respondent to one of the three surveys. The choice sets in each survey version were randomised to avoid order effects that might bias consumers' preference (Day et al., 2012; Liechty et al., 2005). Based on the rule of thumb of Orme (1998), at least 286 respondents were needed per survey when seven choice sets are used. An example choice set as presented to the respondents is given in Fig. 2.

2.4. Econometric model

The basis of DCEs is the random utility theory (Lancaster, 1966). The assumption is that for individual i , the utility of choosing option j ('Option A', 'option B' or 'Neither option A nor B') in a choice situation t is a function of the characteristics of the j alternatives (McFadden,

Table 1
Attributes and levels used in the choice experiment.

Attributes	Levels
Price	€ 1.84 € 5.25 € 8.65 € 12.06
Environmental and ingredient label	Organic label Vegan label Organic and vegan label No label
Nutrition label	Nutri-Score A label No Nutri-Score label
Color	Light to dark yellow Yellow to light green

In the following you are presented seven times with a choice of food products with microalgae proteins. It describes how the products may look like and you are asked each time to indicate your preferred option. Studies showed that consumers tend to act differently when they face hypothetical decisions. In other words, they say one thing and do something different. For example, their willingness to pay for (new developed) food products is higher in a survey than what they are actually willing to pay in real-life situations. Accordingly, it is important that you make each of your upcoming choices like you would if you were actually facing these exact choices in a store, i.e., noting that buying a product means that you would have less money available for other purchases.

Fig. 1. Introduction on the DCE with a cheap talk script.

	Option A	Option B	Neither option A nor B
Concept description	Vegan dry pasta with microalgae proteins (3%) contains no animal ingredients or animal-derived ingredients. The color of the pasta is light to dark yellow depending on the ingredients and type of microalgae that were added.	Vegan dry pasta with microalgae proteins (3%) contains no animal ingredients or animal-derived ingredients. The color of the pasta is yellow to light green , depending on the ingredients and type of microalgae that were added.	
Price/ 500g	€8.65	€5.25	
Label(s)			

Fig. 2. Example of a choice set consisting of two options (Option A or B) and an opt-out option (Neither option A nor B).

1974), which can be represented by Eq. (1):

$$U_{ijt} = \beta x_{ijt} + \epsilon_{ijt} \tag{1}$$

Hereby $i = 1, \dots, n$ is the number of respondents (with $n = 2820$), $j = 1, \dots, J$ (with $J = 2$) is the number of alternatives within a choice situation $t = 1, \dots, T$ (with $T = 7$). The utility functions U_{ijt} are composed of systematic parts β_{ij} , which represent the effects of the alternatives' attributes in the form of an M-dimensional row vector of individual parameters, and a random part, the error term ϵ_{ijt} . This error term stand for the unobserved variables. U is the vector of coefficients containing individual characteristics. The (unobserved) utility is dependent on the choice T_i by individual i . The overall consumers' utility comprises an observed component and a random stochastic component. According to the concept of utility-maximizing behaviour, each respondent will choose the alternative that presents the highest utility for them. They receive utility from products' attributes and not directly from the product itself. Dummy coding was used for the utility estimation for categorical variables.

The first model used in this study is the Multinomial Logit Model (MNL). This model is known to be the simplest model to fit as it assumes homogeneous preferences within a population. Therefore, unobserved factors and their correlation with the model are not taken into account. The random parameters are assumed to be independent and identically distributed. Hereby the presence of identical random parameters means that no covariances or correlations between the J unobserved variables exist (Broeckhoven et al., 2021). The assumption that the distribution faces unobserved effects, is indicated by the identical random parameters (Hensher et al., 2005). The MNL has proven useful in the past but still faces some shortcomings (McFadden & Train, 2000). This model

relies on oversimplifications. As a result, (I) unobserved heterogeneity, (II) independent errors over time and (III) independence from irrelevant alternatives, imply the presence of proportional substitution among alternatives (Ray, 1973). For this study, the utility function for the MNL is shown in Eq. (2):

$$U_{ijt} = \beta_{Nochoice} Nochoice_{ijt} + \beta_{Price} Price_{ijt} + \beta_{Color} Color_{ijt} + \beta_{NL} NL_{ijt} + \beta_{SL} SL_{ijt} + \epsilon_{ijt} \tag{2}$$

Within this equation, $\beta_{No choice}$ represents the Alternative Specific Constant (ASC) of the opt-out option; $Price_{ijt}$ is the price for a package (500 g) of dry pasta with microalgae proteins; NL_{ijt} (nutrition label) is the presence or absence of the Nutri-Score A label on the pasta; SL_{ijt} (sustainability label) is the presence or absence of the organic label or vegan label; $Color_{ijt}$ represents the color 'Yellow to light green' or 'Light to dark yellow'.

An extension of the MNL is the mixed logit model, also known as the Random Parameter Logit model (RPL). This model takes into account the repeated character of respondents' choices, meaning that the random components of the alternatives are allowed to be correlated while the assumption remains that they are identically distributed (Greene, 2008). Previously, the RPL model has been used to analyse DCE data sets (Hempel & Hamm, 2016; Lusk & Schroeder, 2004). For the RPL model in this study, the utility function is shown in Eq. (3).

$$U_{ijt} = \beta_{Nochoice,i} Nochoice_{ijt} + \beta_{Price,i} Price_{ijt} + \beta_{Color,i} Color_{ijt} + \beta_{NL,i} NL_{ijt} + \beta_{SL,i} SL_{ijt} + \epsilon_{ijt} \tag{3}$$

The WTP for a product attribute is the difference between the WTP for a particular product with this attribute and the WTP for an identical

product without that specific attribute (Louviere et al., 2000).

In the econometric model, the coefficients show the effects of each variable on the (unobservable) utility function. Subsequently, based on this principle, the mean WTP for each attribute can be calculated as the marginal rate of substitution between the attributes and the price (Louviere et al., 2000) as shown in Eq. (4):

$$WTP = \beta_k / \beta_{price} \tag{4}$$

Where β_k is the estimated coefficient for the examined attribute and β_{price} is the estimated coefficient for the attribute "Price".

First, the MNL model was applied. This is the simplest model which was used to test whether the model is applicable to the data. Next, the RPL model was applied to test whether there was heterogeneity in the data. It was shown that heterogeneity is present in the data when applying the simplest model, without interactions. The Akaike Information Criterion (AIC) and the Bayesian information criterion (BIC) were used to double-check the relative quality of the models. The lower the AIC and/or the BIC, the better fit the model has. The log-likelihood at convergence was also checked as an indicator of model fit (Greene & Hensher, 2010). Based on this information, it was decided to continue the analyses with the RPL model and no further consideration was given to other models.

2.5. Statistical analyses

Analyses were done in the statistical programs R 4.1.2 and RStudio 2022.07.2. The "mlogit" package was used to convert the data from the DCE to a multinomial format and the "gmnln" package was used to estimate the models (Sarrias et al., 2020).

A reasonable number of pseudo-random draws is needed to have a good approximation of likelihood, consequently better accuracy, to avoid convergence problems (Gu et al., 2013) and a reduction of simulation variance (Bhat, 2001). However, the number should not be too high to reduce computational time. Theoretically, it is difficult to define the minimum number of draws. Therefore, the number (100 in this case) was established based on literature (Balogh et al., 2016; Bhat, 2001; Gu et al., 2013) and on personal experiences. Based on the best-fitting model, mean values for the WTP are calculated with the "wtp.gmnln"-function.

Statistical analyses were performed to evaluate significant associations between categorical variables. The chi-square test was utilized for this purpose. The distribution of ranks between two independent groups was compared using the Mann-Whitney U test. The Kruskal-Wallis test

was used for comparisons between more than two groups. Descriptive statistics were reported to provide a more intuitive representation of the data, including the mean value, even though non-parametric tests were used for multivariate analyses.

3. Results

3.1. Sample characteristics

The total sample consisted of 3027 respondents and sample characteristics are described in Table 2. Respondents are distributed almost equally among the five countries included in this study. About half of the respondents are male (49.0%) and about half of the respondents are female (50.7%). The mean age was 46.32 ± 15.15 years. Consumers who do not follow a specific diet are in the majority (65.7%), followed by a flexitarian diet (29.1%). Most of the respondents indicated to "Get by alright" (41.8%) with respect to their financial situation. Most respondents achieved a secondary educational level (63.8%) followed by bachelor's or higher degree (34.3%). Based on gender, age and region, the sample was representative of the adult population of the Netherlands, Germany, Hungary, Spain and Italy (Table 2).

3.2. Opt-out: who and why?

Some of the respondents who opted out four or more times out of seven choices were excluded from the DCE-analysis, i.e. those who held strongly negative opinions about foods with microalgae proteins, as well as respondents who were not willing to invest the effort required to read and assimilate the information. In total, 17.9% opted out in all of the seven choice sets they were given. 38.6% opted out four or more times because of several reasons (Table 3). Most of the respondents opted out because they found both options too expensive (56.3%). This was followed by the reason that they did not want pasta with microalgae proteins (23.7%). The third most frequently given reason was "I do not like pasta in general" (5.7%).

Some of these reasons given in the questionnaire may indicate that participants are not interested in pasta with microalgae at all. To obtain as fair a picture as possible of willingness to pay, respondents with the following answers on why they opted out were excluded from the willingness to pay analysis: "I do not like pasta in general", "I did not want to read all the information", "I did not see any difference between the two options", "It was too difficult for me to decide" and "I don't like/eat vegan (pasta)" which was a reason given by respondents themselves (Table 3). The removal of these respondents results in a sample of 2820

Table 2

Socio-demographic characteristics of the total sample (n = 3027) in percentages per country for the Netherlands (n = 604) Germany (n = 611), Hungary (n = 606), Spain (n = 603) and Italy (n = 603).

		Total	the Netherlands	Germany	Hungary	Spain	Italy
Gender	Female	50.7	50.0	50.1	52.8	49.7	50.9
	Male	49.0	50.0	49.1	47.2	50.1	48.6
	Other	0.3	0.0	0.8	0.0	0.2	0.5
Age	18 - 29	9.7	10.6	10.1	9.2	9.1	9.1
	30 - 39	16.3	18.0	14.6	16.3	17.1	15.6
	40 - 49	20.0	16.7	15.7	23.8	23.4	20.6
	50 - 59	21.3	20.9	21.8	21.1	20.8	21.9
	60 - 65	17.4	18.2	19.0	16.2	16.3	17.4
	66 - 75	15.3	15.6	18.8	13.4	13.3	15.4
Diet	No restrictions	65.7	65.0	62.0	74.4	68.7	58.7
	Flexitarian	29.1	28.8	31.3	22.3	27.0	36.3
	Pescatarian	2.2	2.6	3.1	1.0	1.8	2.5
	Veg*n	3.0	3.6	3.6	2.3	2.5	2.5
Perceived financial situation	Managing well	34.7	44.2	46.8	18.4	18.8	45.2
	Get by alright	42.6	42.3	34.9	45.4	52.3	38.3
(n = 2971)	Financial difficulties	22.7	13.5	18.3	36.2	28.9	16.5
Education level	Primary education	1.9	2.2	0.9	5.9	0.5	0.2
	Secondary education	63.8	61.7	73.6	83.2	42.0	58.0
	Bachelor's or higher	34.3	36.1	25.5	10.9	57.5	41.8

Table 3
Reasons for choosing opt-out for four or more times the DCE (n = 1167).

	n	Percentage
The two options were often too expensive	657	56.3
I do not want pasta with proteins from microalgae are added	277	23.7
Other reason(s)**	76	6.5
I do not like pasta in general*	67	5.7
It was too difficult for me to decide*	50	4.3
I did not see any difference between the two options*	32	2.8
I did not want to read all the information*	8	0.7

* Respondents who chose one of these reasons to opt-out were left out of the DCE analysis.

** Respondents who mentioned “I don’t like/eat vegan (pasta)” as part of “Other reasons” were left out of the DCE analysis.

respondents for the willingness to pay analyses.

In order to clearly distinguish between respondents who are willing to consider the adoption of foods containing microalgae proteins into their diet and those who do not (based on their opting-out decision), the following paragraphs discuss the differences between these groups in terms of attitudes, socio-demographic characteristics and diets.

Respondents who opted out less than four times scored higher for general health interest ($U = 223698.5$, $p < 0.001$) and environmental concern ($U = 255550$, $p = 0.003$) compared to respondents who opted out four or more times (Fig. 3). The opposite was found for food neophobia ($U = 261613.5$, $p = 0.12$) as respondents who opted out four or more times, had a higher mean food neophobia compared to respondents who opted out less than four times. Lastly, no significant difference between these groups were found for food technology neophobia ($U = 289834$, $p = 0.866$).

The socio-demographics of respondents who opted out at least four out of seven times (n = 1167), are presented in Table 4. Different trends can be observed in the sample of opt-out respondents. Respondents from the Netherlands, Germany and Hungary opted-out significantly more compared to respondents from Italy and Spain, $\chi^2(4, 1167) = 60.12$, $p < 0.001$. The number of respondents who opted out increases with increasing age ($U = 204584$, $p < 0.001$). There was no significant difference between males and females in opting-out, $\chi^2(1, 1188) = 0.07$, $p = 0.792$. Respondents with financial difficulties opted-out significantly more than respondents who manage well or get by alright, $\chi^2(2, 2971) = 26.16$, $p < 0.001$. There is also a significant difference between

opting-out or not depending on education, $\chi^2(2, 1167) = 25.91$, $p < 0.001$. Lastly, respondents with no specific diet opted-out significantly more than respondents with a specific diet (e.g. veg*n, pescetarian etc.), $\chi^2(4, 1167) = 115.59$, $p < 0.001$.

3.3. Willingness to pay for FOP labels on pasta with microalgae proteins

The estimates of the logit model with random parameters is presented in Table 5. The estimate of the price coefficient is significant and negative, indicating that an increase in price decreases the probability of choosing an alternative pasta, which is consistent with microeconomic demand and utility maximization theory. The estimates of the coefficients on the label attributes are significant and positive, suggesting that their presence on pasta with microalgae proteins increases the probability of choosing the alternative. The magnitude of the estimates suggests that the presence of an organic label has the strongest impact on consumer choice, followed by Nutri-Score A and the vegan label. Information about pasta color has a relatively small impact on consumer choice. Results indicate that consumers prefer yellow to light green pasta with microalgae protein over light to dark yellow. It should be noted that although the importance of color as a sensory property of foods with microalgae has already been mentioned, it will not be further elaborated. This is because color was only described verbally as part of the product concept presented to the study participants, whereas no actual product color or color differences were shown.

The WTP of the sample (n = 2820) is shown in Table 6. Respondents were willing to pay more for pasta with microalgae protein if the product had a Nutri-Score A, organic, or vegan label. Respondents were willing to pay the highest premium for the presence of the organic label, i.e. €1.38 more for a pack of pasta with microalgae proteins (500 g) when an organic label was present than when it was not. For the Nutri-Score A label, respondents were willing to pay €1.16 more for the same pack than without the Nutri-Score A label, and finally, respondents are willing to pay €0.89 more for pasta with microalgae proteins with a vegan label. Differences in the described color lead to a difference in WTP, as respondents are willing to pay €0.28 more for pasta with microalgae proteins with a yellow to light green color than for the same pasta with a light to dark yellow color.

Interactions between the WTP for the Nutri-Score label on pasta with microalgae proteins and attitudes showed that when environmental

Fig. 3. Differences in general health interest, food neophobia food technology neophobia and environmental concern, between respondents who opted out less than four times and respondents who opted out four or more times (n = 3027). ^{a-b} Different superscripts indicate a significant difference at the 0.05-level within the same attitude. Confidence intervals based on the standard deviations are shown.

Table 4

Socio-demographic and personal characteristics for respondents who opted-out more than four out of seven times (n = 1167) and separately for The Netherlands (n = 260), Germany (n = 292), Hungary (n = 245), Spain (n = 179) and Italy (n = 191).

		Total	The Netherlands	Germany	Hungary	Spain	Italy
Gender	Female	50.4	48.3	48.3	56.7	48.6	49.2
	Male	49.3	51.0	51.0	43.3	51.4	49.8
	Other	0.3	0.7	0.7	0.0	0.0	1.0
Age	18 – 29	4.1	3.1	3.1	6.1	3.1	5.2
	30 – 39	9.8	6.5	6.5	11.8	6.5	8.4
	40 – 49	17.9	15.8	15.8	18.4	15.8	18.8
	50 – 59	22.5	22.8	22.8	22.9	22.8	19.9
	60 – 65	23.6	27.1	27.1	18.4	27.1	24.1
	66 – 75	22.1	24.7	24.7	22.4	24.7	23.6
Perceived financial situation (n = 1135)	Managing well	31.1	41.2	40.8	11.3	13.9	43.9
	Get by alright	41.4	41.6	35.9	46.2	50.3	35.3
	Financial difficulties	27.5	17.2	23.3	42.5	35.8	20.8
Education level	Primary education	2.0	0.3	0.3	5.7	0.5	0.0
	Secondary education	69.2	76.7	76.7	84.1	49.2	60.2
	Bachelor's or higher	28.8	23.0	23.0	10.2	50.3	39.8
Diet	No restrictions	76.8	73.6	73.6	84.5	83.8	63.4
	Flexitarian	21.3	24.0	24.0	13.9	16.2	34.0
	Pescatarian	0.8	1.4	1.4	0.0	0.0	1.6
	Veg*n	1.1	1.0	1.0	1.6	0.0	1.0

Table 5

Estimates of the RPL model for price, labels and color for pasta with microalgae proteins (n = 2820).

Coefficients	β	S.E.	95% CI	z-value	p-value
Price	-0.34	0.005	[-0.35; -0.33]	-61.71	< 0.001
Nutri-Score A label	0.40	0.048	[0.31; 0.49]	8.32	< 0.001
Organic label	0.48	0.043	[0.40; 0.56]	11.00	< 0.001
Vegan label	0.31	0.042	[0.23; 0.39]	7.32	< 0.001
Color (reference = light to dark yellow)	0.10	0.042	[0.02; 0.18]	2.31	0.021

β represents the coefficient estimates, S.E. represents the standard errors and CI represents the confidence interval, Model fit: Log Likelihood = -15,668, AIC = 3078, BIC = 3117.

concern, FNS, and FTNS increase by one unit, the WTP for pasta with microalgae proteins decreases by €0.58, €0.56, and €0.68, respectively (Table 7). A one unit increase in GHI results in an increase of €1.23. In a similar vein, a one-unit increase in familiarity with foods with microalgae proteins decreases WTP by €0.64. At the same time, an increase in age by one year decreases WTP by €0.06, while females were willing to pay €0.43 more than males. Respondents with a higher income were willing to pay €0.43 more than respondents with an average income. Finally, respondents who are following a veg*n diet were willing to pay €1.44 more for pasta with microalgae protein carrying the Nutri-Score A label than respondents with no specific diet.

The interactions between the WTP for an organic label on pasta with microalgae proteins and attitudes showed a similar trend as for the Nutri-Score label: when environmental concern, FTNS, and FNS increase by one unit, the WTP decreases €0.29, €0.60, and €0.50, respectively (Table 7). By contrast, when GHI increases by one unit, WTP increases by €0.88. When familiarity with foods with microalgae proteins increases by one unit, WTP decreases by €0.66. Among sociodemographic characteristics, only age showed a significant interaction with WTP for

the organic label, as WTP decreased by €0.06 when age increased by one year. Finally, veg*ns were found to have an additional WTP of €1.09 when the organic label was present compared to consumers who do not have a no dietary restrictions or consumers with another diet.

A one-unit increase in environmental concern and FTNS resulted in a decrease of WTP for a vegan label on pasta with microalgae proteins by €0.47 and €0.41 respectively. However, a one-unit increase in GHI resulted in a €0.87 increase in WTP for pasta with microalgae proteins carrying a vegan label (Table 7). When familiarity increases by one unit, WTP for a vegan label decreases by €0.43. Interactions between WTP and sociodemographic characteristics showed that, first, WTP for a vegan label decreases by €0.06 per year as respondents get older. Second, females were willing to pay €0.37 compared to men. Third, respondents with the highest degree (i.e., bachelor's degree or higher) were willing to pay €0.42 more than respondents with a lower education (i.e., secondary education). The results on the interactions between the WTP for a vegan label on pasta with microalgae proteins and dietary pattern show that both flexitarians and veg*ns were willing to pay €0.43 and €3.15 more respectively, than respondents who do not follow a

Table 6

WTP for a nutrition label (Nutri-Score A-label), sustainability labels (organic and vegan) and color (n = 2820) on pasta with microalgae proteins.

	Mean	SE	95% CI	t-value	p-value
Nutri-Score label	1.16	0.14	[1.15; 1.17]	8.34	< 0.001
Organic label	1.38	0.13	[1.38; 1.38]	11.04	< 0.001
Vegan label	0.89	0.12	[0.89; 0.89]	7.41	< 0.001
Color (reference = light to dark yellow)	0.28	0.12	[0.28; 0.28]	-2.31	0.021
Opt-out	4.91	0.11	[4.91; 4.91]	42.76	< 0.001

SE = Standard Error; CI = Confidence interval; Significance at a 0.05-level.

Table 7

Interactions between the WTP for the Nutri-Score, organic and vegan label with attitudes and socio-demographics (n = 2820).

Willingness to pay	β	SE	t-value	p-value
Nutri-Score \times Environmental concern	-0.58	0.135	4.27	< 0.001
Nutri-Score \times General Health Interest	1.23	0.142	-8.66	< 0.001
Nutri-Score \times Food Neophobia	-0.56	0.144	3.92	< 0.001
Nutri-Score \times Food Technology Neophobia	-0.68	0.114	6.00	< 0.001
Nutri-Score \times Familiarity	-0.64	0.066	9.62	< 0.001
Nutri-Score \times Age	-0.06	0.006	8.96	< 0.001
Nutri-Score \times Female	-0.43	0.180	2.43	0.015
Nutri-Score \times Highest education	-0.16	0.189	0.83	0.407
Nutri-Score \times Highest income	0.43	0.185	-2.32	0.020
Nutri-Score \times Flexitarian	0.25	0.196	-1.26	0.207
Nutri-Score \times Veg*n	1.44	0.471	-3.05	0.002
Organic \times Environmental concern	-0.29	0.132	2.22	0.026
Organic \times General Health Interest	0.88	0.139	-6.34	< 0.001
Organic \times Food Neophobia	-0.60	0.139	4.29	< 0.001
Organic \times Food Technology Neophobia	-0.50	0.113	4.40	< 0.001
Organic \times Familiarity	-0.66	0.064	10.25	< 0.001
Organic \times Age	-0.06	0.006	9.71	< 0.001
Organic \times Female	-0.23	0.174	1.34	0.180
Organic \times Highest education	0.33	0.18	-1.89	0.075
Organic \times Highest income	-0.19	0.181	1.04	0.297
Organic \times Flexitarian	0.04	0.193	-0.22	0.826
Organic \times Veg*n	1.09	0.432	-2.52	0.012
Vegan \times Environmental concern	-0.47	0.125	3.71	< 0.001
Vegan \times General Health Interest	0.87	0.132	-6.59	< 0.001
Vegan \times Food Neophobia	-0.19	0.133	1.42	0.157
Vegan \times Food Technology Neophobia	-0.41	0.105	3.88	< 0.001
Vegan \times Familiarity	-0.43	0.061	7.05	< 0.001
Vegan \times Age	-0.06	0.006	10.30	< 0.001
Vegan \times Female	-0.37	0.166	2.22	0.027
Vegan \times Highest education	0.42	0.174	-2.44	0.015
Vegan \times Highest income	0.25	0.171	-1.44	0.151
Vegan \times Flexitarian	0.43	0.181	-2.40	0.017
Vegan \times Veg*n	3.15	0.434	-7.28	< 0.001

SE = Standard Error; CI = Confidence interval; Significance at a 0.05-level.

specific dietary pattern.

4. Discussion

4.1. Opting-out: who and why?

Approximately one-sixth of respondents opted out of the DCE all seven times, while more than one-third opted out four or more times out of seven. These results were compared to previous studies in which [Michaud et al. \(2013\)](#) found that 32.5% of their sample opted out of the majority of choice sets in a choice experiment on the WTP for roses. By contrast, [Hoefkens et al. \(2012\)](#) found that only 11% of respondents chose to opt out when investigating nutrition labels in a catering environment. Compared to previous studies, the number of respondents who opted-out was thus relatively high in the present study. A possible explanation is that foods with microalgae proteins may not yet appeal to a substantial share of contemporary consumers. Sensory properties have been identified as important determinants of the acceptance of foods with alternative proteins ([Hartmann et al., 2015](#); [Verbeke, 2015](#)). A plausible assumption is that consumers lack sufficient sensory experience with microalgae proteins, resulting in an insufficient information base to form an accurate picture of pasta with microalgae proteins. This lack of familiarity and information could contribute to the relatively high opt-out rate observed in this study.

The most frequently cited reason among respondents who opted out in more than four out of seven choices was "The two options were too expensive." Conventional dry pasta is on average about ten times cheaper than its microalgae proteins counterparts anno 2022, so with

the current rising cost of living in Europe, consumers may want to save on extras or buy cheaper food options and not see or consider the health/environmental benefits of a more expensive option like pasta with microalgae proteins. The second most important reason to opt out was that they did not want pasta with microalgae proteins. This could be due to the fact that consumers know little about foods containing microalgae proteins and that these proteins are not yet well enough known in the general population. A third important reason was "I do not want pasta with proteins from microalgae added". These results suggest that consumers need to be better informed about the potential health and environmental benefits of foods with microalgae proteins. The fourth most important reason was "I don't like/eat vegan (pasta)." This can be firstly explained by consumer ignorance since most pasta in northern European countries is vegan (i.e., does not contain eggs), but consumers may not be informed and aware about this. A second and more plausible reason may be that consumers know that pasta is mostly vegan, but do not really care about this or still have a preference for non-vegan foods. Finally, the explicit "vegan" claim may eventually also repel some consumers or at least induce some hesitation to consider the concerned product.

Because the number of opt-outs was so high, it was decided to look more closely at the characteristics of respondents who opted out four or more times compared to respondents who opted out less than four times. Environmental concern and GHI were higher among respondents who opted out less than four times, while FN was higher among respondents who opted out four or more times. In terms of sociodemographic characteristics, respondents from the Netherlands, Germany, and Hungary were more likely to choose not to eat pasta with microalgae proteins

than respondents from Italy and Spain. This could be due to the fact that foods with microalgae proteins are more widely consumed in Southern European countries than in Central and Northern European countries. In addition, the number of respondents who opted out increased with age. This may be due to the fact that older consumers are less familiar with foods with microalgae proteins. Regarding gender, no significant difference was found between consumers who opted-out four or more times and consumers who opted-out less than four times. Previously, it was also shown that gender does not significantly affect food WTP (Urala & Lähteenmäki, 2007). Respondents who had financial difficulties opted out more than consumers with better incomes. This could be because the prices in the choice experiment tended to be high and respondents with lower incomes did not want to pay as much and therefore did not further consider the choice. Finally, respondents who did not follow a particular dietary pattern opted out more frequently compared to respondents with a particular dietary pattern (e.g., veg*ns). This could be due to the fact that consumers who do not follow a specific diet are not interested in innovative foods with alternative proteins and prefer to maintain their eating habits.

4.2. Willingness to pay for FOP labels

WTP for FOP labels on pasta with microalgae proteins and interactions between WTP for labels with attitudes, sociodemographic characteristics and diets were examined, as done also previously by Plasek and Temesi (2019). Several characteristics appeared to be significant and therefore explain the heterogeneity of preferences for the Nutri-Score, organic label, and vegan label on pasta with microalgae proteins. The first hypothesis that adding labels such as Nutri-Score A, Organic, or Vegan label on pasta with microalgae proteins increases consumers' willingness to pay is confirmed. The second hypothesis is also confirmed as different attitudinal, socio-demographic and dietary characteristics showed to have a significant impact on the willingness to pay for pasta with microalgae proteins.

The presence of the Nutri-Score A label leads to an increased WTP for pasta with microalgae proteins. This result is consistent with previous research that has also shown that the presence of a favorable Nutri-Score increases WTP for (healthier) foods carrying the label (Gassler et al., 2023; Nabec et al., 2019; Sampalean et al., 2021). To our knowledge, the interactions between attitudes, sociodemographic characteristics, and dietary habits with the Nutri-Score have not been investigated prior to this study.

Respondents' WTP for pasta with microalgae proteins was found to be increased by the presence of the organic label. These results are consistent with previous research showing that consumers are willing to pay a premium for organic and environmentally friendly products (Batte et al., 2007; Loureiro et al., 2002; Tranter et al., 2009). Specifically, consumers are more willing to pay more for foods with an organic label than for similar products without an organic label (Akaichi et al., 2012; Hasselbach & Roosen, 2015), which is consistent with the results of recent studies for organic pasta (Chronakis & Madsen, 2011; Nilsson & Vahtra, 2017). Consumers who are concerned about the environment were willing to pay more for foods with an organic label already in the study by Loureiro et al. (2001). Veg*ns show a remarkably high WTP for the organic label on pasta with microalgae proteins, indicating their heightened concern about and interest in organic foods. Consumers with higher incomes (Loureiro et al., 2001), as well as women compared to men (Bellows et al., 2008; Vecchio et al., 2016) were also willing to pay more for organic-labelled products in previous studies, although these effects were not demonstrated in the present study.

Respondents were willing to pay more for a vegan label on pasta with microalgae proteins compared to the same pasta without a vegan label. This is in line with previous research showing that consumers are willing to pay a premium price for vegan breadsticks (Marangon et al., 2016). Significant negative interactions were found between the presence of the vegan label and environmental concern, FTNS, familiarity, higher age

and females compared to males. On the contrary, the higher the GHI, the higher the willingness to pay. The same accounts for educations as the highest education has a higher willingness to pay compared to average education. Flexitarians and veg*ns are willing to pay more for pasta with microalgae proteins compared to consumers without a specific dietary pattern. The European Vegetarian Union (2021) found that consumers who are looking for vegan products are willing to pay more for these products with a vegan label. This has been confirmed in the present study as veg*ns were willing to pay more for a vegan label on pasta with microalgae proteins compared to consumers without a specific dietary pattern.

4.3. Limitations

The first limitation of this study is related to the description of the product concept used in the DCE. Pasta with microalgae proteins was explicitly presented as vegan. While most pasta in countries like Germany, the Netherlands, and Hungary is vegan, some respondents might have misunderstood that the pasta was different than what they commonly consume, since one of the frequently reported opt-out reasons was that they did not like vegan (pasta).

Secondly, the results of the WTP analysis should be interpreted with caution as it has already been shown that the WTP is greater in hypothetical settings relative to incentive-compatible settings (List & Gallet, 2001; Murphy et al., 2005). Adding to the hypothetical setting of the present study is the fact that the same prices and price ranges were used in all countries. While this approach allowed us to examine the willingness to pay among the entire sample, this approach may have overlooked potential variations in pricing patterns among different countries. Factors such as local market conditions and cost of living could influence the actual prices of vegan pasta in each country. By using a uniform price, the true market dynamics and consumer preferences specific to individual countries may not have been fully captured. The actual product was also not shown during concept testing. The color of the products was only described verbally. This means that the study could not properly assess the potential effects of visual attributes on participants' perceptions and valuations. The use of a color scale as part of the concept description could have been a useful alternative.

Thirdly, one aspect that was not considered in this study is the potential disgust that can act as a barrier to food consumption, as it is a significant influencing factor in the acceptance of alternative protein sources such as insects in general, and insect burgers and buffalo worms in specific (Ammann et al., 2018; Lammers et al., 2019). It remains to be investigated whether disgust is also a relevant factor in the case of microalgae.

5. Conclusion and implications

This study has demonstrated that consumers have an interest in, and are willing to pay more for nutrition (Nutri-Score), environmental (organic), and ingredient (vegan) labels on pasta with microalgae proteins. The results have implications regarding the use of the Nutri-Score, organic and vegan labels on products with microalgae proteins for food producers and can provide recommendations to policymakers and food producers. Considering the marginal WTP for the three researched labels, when producers want to increase the WTP of their products, they may consider adding a Nutri-Score, organic or vegan label, if applicable for the product. Furthermore, campaigns should highlight the nutritional and environmental benefits of microalgae proteins in foods. This way, they can boost consumers' confidence in microalgae proteins and increase the purchase and consumption of products containing microalgae proteins.

The results of the study suggest a positive relationship between the presence of a Nutri-Score A-label and consumer willingness to pay for pasta with microalgae proteins. In Europe, there are several initiatives aimed at making the Nutri-Score label mandatory. One of these

initiatives is a scientific report endorsed by a group of 320 scientists and health experts that advocates for the adoption of the Nutri-Score as a standardized and mandatory nutrition label for Europe. The report highlights the effectiveness of labelling as a public health tool based on sound science (EU scientists and health professionals for Nutri-Score, 2023). In response to these initiatives, the European Commission has announced its intention to revise Regulation (EU) No. 1169/2011 with the aim of introducing a uniform and mandatory nutrition labelling system. The Nutri-Score has emerged as the preferred choice in the context of this proposed regulation (European Parliament, 2023). Our study contributes to the existing body of knowledge by showing that consumers have a positive attitude toward the Nutri-Score label. The willingness to pay a price premium for pasta with microalgae proteins when labelled with a Nutri-Score label speaks to the effectiveness and consumer acceptance of this labelling system. This could encourage manufacturers to label their products with a (positive) Nutri-Score label and thus inform consumers about healthier foods. This, in turn, may lead to small changes in consumer diets in a desired (more healthy and sustainable) sense.

Organic food prices are higher than conventional food prices (Askew, 2021). For consumers seeking organic products, the presence of an organic label can add value. It immediately indicates that the product is organic and gives a clear indication of any additional price that may be expected. It may also help those who are willing to pay a premium for organic products but have difficulty finding or identifying them. Consequently, labelling could serve as an incentive for organic food producers to promote their products. In addition, our study revealed which sociodemographic consumer groups would be willing to pay a price premium for organic products. From these results, we found that veg*ns in particular were willing to pay more. In order to make organic foods more accessible to the entire population, organic food producers may need to lower their prices. Although the European organic label is mandatory for most organic foods (European Commission, 2018), it is not known whether consumers are aware of the diversity in the assortment of these foods.

Finally, the presence of a vegan label significantly increases the willingness to pay for pasta with microalgae proteins, at least among consumers who are open to this food category. Therefore, policy should prioritize the adoption of the vegan label to increase acceptance and market demand for vegan products. In addition, public and private policy efforts should ensure that affordable and accessible vegan options are available to a wide range of consumers, including those with lower incomes. It is worth noting that, contrary to popular belief, a plant-based diet is generally less expensive than an omnivorous diet (Pais et al., 2022). This is an opportunity for omnivorous consumers, including those with lower incomes, to choose more vegan options, with the vegan label serving as a motivating factor and easy decision rule.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Hélène Van der Stricht: Conceptualization, Data curation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Validation, Visualization, Writing – original draft. **Adriano Profeta:** Conceptualization, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Methodology, Writing – review & editing. **Yung Hung:** Conceptualization, Data curation, Investigation, Methodology, Supervision, Writing – review & editing. **Wim Verbeke:** Conceptualization, Funding acquisition, Investigation, Methodology, Supervision, Writing – review & editing.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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